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OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF KARNATAKA STATE FINANCIAL CORPORATION: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT:

Indian banking system has transformed in recent years due to globalization in the world market, which has resulted in fierce competition. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the operational performance of Karnataka State Financial Corporation. Analytical frame of the operational aspects in terms of the sanctions and disbursements in general, and to different sectors, purposes; and also the trends over the period under study have been presented. In addition, the financial performance is evaluated by the identified parameters and bench marks." The study is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of KSFC for the study period i.e. 2000-01 to 2012-13. Ratios, t-test, z-test correlation analysis have been used to analyze the present data. The study suggested that KSFC should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt and improving the productive efficiency of employees.

KEY WORDS: *Financial Performance, Operational Performance, Profitability.*

INTRODUCTION:

The mandate given in the statue drives the corporation to develop entrepreneurship, bring in balanced regional development and drive the industrialization in the state in order to bring the economic development besides creating employment. The quantum of sanctions is one of the indicators, which throw light on the performance of the corporation in fulfilling the responsibilities cast on them.

It cannot be said that the corporation has performed the business unless the sanctions made by the corporation is converted into disbursements. Generally, there will time lag between the sanction projects. The other notable reasons could be the delay in obtaining necessary approvals from government agencies has also delay in obtaining the required machinery in time. The projects coming up in backward areas times occur due to non-availability of proper infrastructure to implement the projects.

Prior to liberalization, the State Financial Corporations were on the 'growth' mode and there was no competition for them in the segment of financing term loans to tiny, small and medium enterprises. They were concentrating mostly on encouraging first generation entrepreneurs and they were taking the risk in financing as there was no concept of taking collateral securities. This project oriented approach and 'growth-of State of Karnataka. Some of the industrialization international reputations have taken seeds from Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

This paper provides a specific analytical focus on the operational and financial performance of the KSFC. Analytical frame work of the operational aspects in terms of the sanction, disbursements, out standings and Recoveries in general, and to

operational performance indicators; and also the trends over the period. i.e. from 2000-01 to 2012-13 have been presented.

PROFILE OF KSFC:

Karnataka State Financial Corporation was established in March 1959 under section 3(1) of the State Financial Corporations Act, 1951 with the main objectives of promoting and developing industrial growth in the State of Karnataka by providing financial assistance in the form of term loans, equity participation, equipment leasing etc. In the recent years, the activities have been mainly confined to term lending catering to small and medium scale industries. The Corporation, headquartered at Bangalore, with seven Zonal Offices and 30 Branch Offices is headed by a Chairman and the Managing Director nominated by the State Government, who is assisted by two Executive Directors and six General Managers.

KSFC gives financial assistance to set up tiny, small, medium and large scale industrial units in the Karnataka State. The Corporation extends term loans to new & existing units up to Rs. 500 lakhs for corporate bodies and registered co-operative societies. Term loans up to Rs. 200 lakhs are sanctioned to proprietary, partnership and joint Hindu undivided family concerns. KSFC extends lease financial assistance and hire purchase assistance for acquisition of machinery/equipment/transport vehicles. KSFC has a merchant banking department and is approved as a category - I merchant banker by SEBI. Under this activity it does management of public issues, under-writing of shares, project report preparation, deferred payment guarantee, syndication of loans, bill discounting etc. The fund based activities like subscription to non-convertible debentures, factoring services are also considered.

KSFC is one of the fast track term lending financial institutions in the country. With assistance to more than 1, 56,758 units amounting to nearly 7,744 crores over the last 47 years in the State of Karnataka, it is one of the robust, professionally managed State Financial Corporations.

The focus of Karnataka State Financial Corporation (KSFC) has always been on the small scale sector, artisans, tiny units and disadvantaged groups. KSFC has been the main term lending institution in most of the districts for first generation entrepreneurs. Its area of activities are:

- Assistance to backward areas
- Assistance to the small scale sector
- Assistance to artisans, tiny, village and cottage industries.
- Assistance to medium scale industries
- Assistance to local entrepreneurs
- Assistance to special segments of society

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

Main objectives of the Paper is as follows

- To study and analyze the operational performance of Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

- To identify impact of profitability on operational activities of Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES:

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

- H₁: There is no significant difference between Sanctions and Disbursements of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.
- H₂: There is no significant difference between Disbursement and Out standings of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.
- H₃: There is no significant difference between Disbursement and Recoveries of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

METHODOLOGY:

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature and covers the period of 13 years from 2000 to 2013. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, via 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data was collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions regarding different financial and operational aspects of the KSFC.

The study was based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports, budgets, manuals and also the annual reports of KSFC. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the RBI Reports and Government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, correlation, Regression, t-test, skewness, and kurtosis are used for this study. For this study, the statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

PERFORMANCE OF KSFC :

The mirror for success of an organization is its performance and its results. The performance, only the positive performance and nothing but the productive performance shall make an organization to prove it successful. Its operations should result surplus value in particular, the materialistic values in nature and not the progress and development by monetary figures in general. The operational

performance involves with and revolves around important factor, finance. Thus the operational performance will be cheerful along with simultaneous movement of finance factor. The outcome of inter-relationship of finance and operations are dealt in this paper with a comparative study of different operations under Financial Analysis and Ratio Analysis is the tool to focus light on the different results of Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

PERFORMANCE INDICATORS:

To evaluate performance of KSFC during the period 2000 to 2013 considered the performance Para meters; those are Operating Profit per Employee, Net Profit per Employee, Sanctions per Employee, EPS per Shareholders, Return on Assets. These are analyzed here under.

1. Operating Profit per Employee = Operating Profit/ No. Employee
2. Net Profit per Employee = Net Profit/ No. Employee
3. Sanction per Employee = Sanctions/ No. Employee
4. Earnings per Share = Earnings/ No. of Equity Shares
5. Return on Assets= Profit After Tax/ Total Assets

Table: 1 Performance Indicators of KSFC

Year	Operating Profit Per Employee	Net Profit Per Employee	Sanctions Per Employee	EPS Per Shareholders	Return on Assets
2000 - 01	-2.7	-7.4	31.34	105.52	-1.72
2001 - 02	-2.5	-10	21.91	143.74	-0.13
2002 - 03	-0.5.2	-10.22	25.29	142	-3.2
2003 - 04	1.0	6	22.70	0.9	0.68
2004 - 05	0.5	0.2	18.68	2.8	0.37
2005 - 06	0.6	0.4	24.68	8.012	0.52
2006 - 07	1.3	1.0	33.56	13.23	1.41
2007 - 08	2.5	5.0	29.96	63.52	1.99

2008 - 09	0.6	-3.3	46.87	-40.71	0.42
2009 - 10	0.8	0.2	54.38	0.98	0.49
2010 - 11	1.9	1.9	64.52	23.33	0.27
2011-12	1.0	1.0	73.70	11.33	0.35
2012-13	1.1	1.5	87.74	17.39	0.49
Mean	0.43	-1.055	41.18	34.85	0.15
SD	1.52	5.20	22.36	57.92	1.31
T	1.02	-0.73	6.64	2.36	0.41
p-values	0.327	0.479	0.000	0.036	0.689

Source: Computed based on Annual Reports of KSFC from 2000-01 to 2012-13.

INFERENCE:

It is seen from the table that the performance of KSFC operating profit per employee and net profit per employee has been fluctuating trend. Sanction per employee is also increasing trend during the study period. It indicates that profitability and performance of the KSFC has been increased year to year. EPS and Return on Assets is progressive trend. Mean Operating Profit and Net Profit per employee is 0.43 times and -1.055 times respectively, where sanctions per employee are 41.18 times. EPS and ROA average is 34.85 and 0.15 times. Highest and lowest standard deviations are 57.92 and 1.31 times with respect to the EPS and ROA. For t - Test values and p-values of sanctions per employee and EPS are significant and given model is a good fit for the data. Other three indicators i.e. Net profit per employee, operating profit per employee and Return on investment are not significant. Overall performance of Corporation is satisfactory during the study period.

OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF KSFC:

This part of the study provides a specific analytical focus on the operational performance of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation. This paper is straight way analytical frame of the operational aspects in terms of the sanctions, disbursements, outstandings and Recoveries in general, and to different sectors, purposes examining operational aspects of KSFC and then testing the resulting ideas and hypotheses empirically over the period.

Table 2 STATEMENT OF OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF KSFC

Year	Sanctions	Disbursement	outstanding Recoveries	Disbursement to Sanctions	Outstanding to Disbursement	Recoveries to Disbursement
2000-01	440.65	328.78	187.84	0.75	0.56	1.70
2001-02	503.71	429.42	186.88	0.96	0.64	0.82
2002-03	340.67	285.28	259.72	0.79	0.66	1.08
2003-04	302.55	245.79	186.63	0.62	0.61	1.03
2004-05	242.87	210.34	166.62	0.92	0.65	1.08
2005-06	316.20	192.86	132.64	0.63	0.66	1.03
2006-07	424.52	310.39	250.27	0.73	0.43	1.16
2007-08	368.13	301.13	226.08	0.68	0.41	1.17
2008-09	565.24	387.92	337.54	0.69	0.33	1.31
2009-10	631.49	434.39	335.68	0.69	0.32	1.38
2010-11	731.62	580.4	399.91	0.72	0.28	1.02
2011-12	817.32	597.06	375.36	0.78	0.29	1.11
2012-13	944.06	734.73	423.0	0.78	0.26	1.08
Mean	494.51	378.65	188.55	0.67	0.47	1.03
SD	233.99	162.96	24.06	0.31	0.17	0.33
Skewness	0.887	1.15	-0.014	0.913	-1.72	0.009
Kurtosis	-0.434	0.26	-1.65	0.101	2.11	-1.97

Source: Computed based on Annual Report of KSFC from 2000-01 to 2012-13

FIGURE - 1

FIGURE - 2

FIGURE - 3

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES:

CORRELATION ANALYSIS:

Correlation is concern describing the strength of relationship between two variables. In this study the correlation co-efficient analysis is undertaken to find out the relationship between Disbursement and Sanctions, Disbursement and Outstanding and Outstanding and Recoveries of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

The measure of correlation is called the co-efficient of correlation. It is denoted by 'r' and the simplest formula for computing the appropriate t value by using difference test considering variables with respect to KSFC.

TEST OF SIGNIFICANCE:

H₁: There is no significant difference between Sanctions and Disbursements of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

Table: 3

Correlation and t-test results for Sanctions and Disbursements				
'r' value	Correlation result	Co-efficient(r ²)	't' value	Hypothesis result
0.98	Highly Positive	0.96	/16.46/	Rejected and in Significant

Source: Computed.

ANOVA TABLE

Model	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	575961.036	1	575961.036	242.644	.000 ^a
Residual	26110.569	11	2373.688		
Total	602071.604	12			

a. Predictors: (Constant), disbursement

b. Dependent Variable: sanctions

Table-3 reveals that the correlation between Sanctions and Disbursements is high correlation. The co-efficient determinations of Sanctions and Disbursements are 0.98. That is 96.04% of variance in the Sanctions is accounted by Disbursement.

For t-test and F-test results, it is clear that the computed value is more than critical value at 5% level of significance and F value is also supported this, where more significance (.000) is seen. Therefore, given null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between Sanctions and Disbursements. This is justified that correlations exist between Sanctions and Disbursements.

H₂: There is no significant difference between Disbursement and Outstandings of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

Table: 4

Correlation and t-test results for Disbursement and out standings

r' value	Correlation result	Co-efficient(r ²)	t' value	Hypothesis result
0.37	Highly Positive	0.1369	/1.32/	Accepted and significant

ANOVA TABLE

Source: Computed.

Model	Sum of Squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	43780.957	1	43780.957	1.752	.213 ^a
Residual	274957.362	11	24996.124		
Total	318738.318	12			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Outstanding

b. Dependent Variable: Disbursements

Table-4 reveals that the correlation between Outstandings and Disbursements is a positive correlation. The co-efficient determinations of Outstandings and Disbursements are 0.1369. That is 13.69% of variance in the Outstandings is accounted by Disbursement.

For t-test and F-test results, it is clear that the computed value is less than critical value at 5% level of significance and F value is also supported this, where insignificance (.213) is seen. Therefore, given null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between Outstandings and Disbursements. This is justified that correlations exist between Outstandings and Disbursements.

H₃: There is no significant difference between disbursement and Recoveries of the Karnataka State Financial Corporation.

Table: 5

Correlation and t-test results for Disbursement and Recoveries

r' value	Correlation result	Co-efficient(r ²)	t' value	Hypothesis result
0.19	Positive	0.038	/0.64/	Accepted and significant

ANOVA TABLE

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	298419.962	1	298419.962	161.559	.000 ^a

Residual	20318.356	11	1847.123	
Total	318738.318	12		

a. Predictors: (Constant),

Recoveries,

b. Dependent Variable:
Disbursements

Source: Computed.

Table-5 reveals that the correlation between Recoveries and Disbursements is positive correlation. The co-efficient determinations of Sanctions and Disbursements are 0.038. That is 3.8% of variance in the Recoveries is accounted by Disbursement. For t-test and F-test results, it is clear that the computed value is less than critical value at 5% level is significant, but F value is not supported this, even though it is having more significance value (000). Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted. Further, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between Recoveries and Disbursements. This is justified that the correlations exist between Recoveries and Disbursements.

CONCLUSION:

This paper presents the major findings of the operational and financial performance of KSFC over a period of thirteen years from 2001-2002 to 2012-2013.

- It is observed that corporation has sufficient funds to meet its risk profile. It generates more funds and utilized purposefully.
- KSFC is an effective control of Non Performing Assets over its Advances.
- It observed that corporation net profit per employee performance is improved year to year.
- Net profit after tax of the corporation has been decreased in between year 2010 to 2013.
- It can be seen that assets quality is not satisfactory during the study period.
- It is found that more liquidity has been maintained by KSFC during the year 2009-13.
- It is observed that Liquidity Position of KSFC is good.

To conclude, our findings from the operational and financial performance of KSFC are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that KSFC should emphasize on the productive efficiency of employees. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the corporation for better performance.

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